

**THE SPECIES COMPOSITION AND ANTIBIOTIC SENSITIVITY IN
MICROORGANISMS FROM MAXILLARY SINUS AND OTHER BIOTOPES OF THE
MAXILLOFACIAL AREA DETECTED DURING SINUS-LIFT PROCEDURE**

Mochalov Iurii – MD, DrMedSc, Full Professor, Professor of the Department of Surgical Dentistry and Clinical Disciplines, Uzhhorod National University, Uzhhorod, Ukraine, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5654-1725>

Kryvtsova Maryna – DrBiolSc, Full Professor, Chief of the Department of Clinical-Laboratory and Morpho-Functional Diagnostics, Uzhhorod National University, Uzhhorod, Ukraine, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8454-2509>

Tsuperiak Serhii – MD, PhD, Teacher of the Department of Dentistry of Post-Diploma Education, Uzhhorod National University, Uzhhorod, Ukraine, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6897-5037>

Myhajlichenko Bohdan – MD, PhD student, Department of Therapeutical Dentistry, National University of Health Care named by P. L. Shupik, Kyiv, Ukraine, <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0001-1921>

Guzo Nutsu – MD, PhD student, Department of Surgical Dentistry and Clinical Disciplines, Uzhhorod National University, Uzhhorod, Ukraine, <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1409-6028>

Kizim Alla – MD, MBA, Assistant Professor of the Department of Pediatrics, Obstetrics and Gynecology, Educational and Scientific Center “Institute of Biology and Medicine”, Taras Shevchenko Kyiv National University, Kyiv, Ukraine, <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6037-2607>

Corresponding author: Iurii Mochalov, MD, DMedSc, Full Professor, Professor of the Department of Surgical Dentistry and Clinical Disciplines, Uzhhorod National University, 16A, Universytetska str., Uzhhorod, Ukraine, 88015 yuriy.mochalov@uzhnu.edu.ua, u.mochalov@gmail.com
+380661225402

ABSTRACT

Aim. Determination of the species composition of the four biotopes in maxillofacial region (pharynx, nasal passage, oral mucosa, and Schneiderian membrane) from pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic microorganisms and their sensitivity to antibiotics during sinus lift procedure.

Materials and methods. Biological material (swabs) was studied using the bacteriological method by cultivation on standard and differential diagnostic nutrient media; antibiotic sensitivity of the isolated strains was determined using the disk diffusion method.

Results. The studies allowed us to identify an ambiguous picture in the population of different biotopes of the maxillofacial area with bacteria and fungi. In the maxillary sinus, without clinical signs of inflammation, pathogenic microorganisms were present in clinically significant concentrations, mainly *Streptococci*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and fungi of the genus *Candida*. The most effective on the germs isolated in clinically significant concentrations were Ceftriaxone and Cefoperazone/Sulbactam. Among the cultures, $\frac{3}{4}$ were sensitive to Cefuroxime. Gatifloxacin seemed to be quite effective; sensitivity and moderate sensitivity cases were distributed equally, without resistance. The fungi found on the mucoperiosteum of the maxillary sinus were sensitive to Fluconazole, Ketoconazole and Clotrimazole, moderately sensitive to Itraconazole and Nystatin.

Conclusions. The results indicate a tendency to narrow the possibilities of choosing antibacterial agents for a prophylactic course when performing sinus lift surgery.

Keywords: maxillary sinus, oral cavity, microbiome, sinus lift, antimicrobial resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Replacement of dentition defects with implant-supported prosthetic structures is widely used in clinical practice and is considered the “gold standard” of functional rehabilitation of dental patients. It has significant, proven advantages compared to traditional bridges and removable dentures, in terms of long-term functioning and quality of life for patients. However, in clinical practice, dental surgeons often face the problem of bone supply deficiency and the lack of the necessary volume of bone tissue to install dental implants in the desired prosthetic position. This problem is prevalent in the lateral zones of the upper jaw and is the main limiting factor in the application of modern methods of replacing dentition defects [1, 2]. The proximity of the maxillary sinus limits the possibility of installing an implant of the required length in the optimal prosthetic position. Also, it increases the risk of complications arising during surgery in patients with an edentulous upper jaw. It is well-known that among patients with a pneumatic type of upper jaw structure, the maxillary sinus fills the alveolar process and causes the phenomenon of “counter resorption”, when, when teeth are lost, the alveolar bone is lost both from the oral cavity and from the maxillary sinus [3, 4].

Restoring the required volume and quality of alveolar bone in this anatomically and functionally complex area is a difficult clinical task that may be solved in various ways; however, the most common of them, according to many studies, is lateral sinus floor augmentation (open sinus lift). This technique was once proposed by H. Tatum (1974) and later improved by Boyne P, James RA (1986) and other authors. The lateral sinus floor augmentation operations, according to their recommendations, involved performing an osteotomy of the lateral wall of the maxillary sinus with subsequent careful elevation of the muco-periosteal membrane of the sinus, and creating a space that was filled with autologous bone graft or other bone-substituting material, sometimes simultaneously with the installation of dental implants. The authors initially used only autologous bone graft. The first intervention was performed by H. Tatum simultaneously with the installation of endosseous implants. Later, P. Boyne and R.A. James recommended a two-stage technique with delayed installation of dental implants after 6 months [5, 6, 1, 2].

Many years of experience using lateral sinus floor augmentation in clinical practice allow us to consider it a procedure characterized by high efficiency and the predictability of its results. Even though lateral sinus floor augmentation is regarded as a reasonably safe and predictable procedure, the literature data indicate the possibility of developing intra- and postoperative complications associated with this operation. Among the most threatening complications, the authors highlight the development of acute and chronic maxillary sinusitis, which is often associated with infection and complete loss of bone grafts or bone substitute material. The authors determine the frequency of acute maxillary sinusitis at 10–26%, while the frequency of graft loss, according to the authors, is lower (3–10%), since some infectious complications in the case of timely diagnosis and the use of the correct treatment tactics may be effectively eliminated and its negative consequences are minimized. Chronicity of the inflammatory process is noted in 1.3–5% of cases. However, the number of works devoted to the study of this complication in lateral sinus floor augmentation is limited, and their results are contradictory [7, 8, 9, 1].

Some researchers claim that the maxillary sinuses are usually a sterile anatomical site. According to other authors, a healthy maxillary sinus is not sterile. In clinically healthy adult patients, it is generally slightly contaminated with transient bacteria, since a small number of inflammatory cells in the thickness of the maxillary sinus mucosa is a normal state of the respiratory tract defense system. The nasal cavity is dominated by saprophytic and opportunistic microflora, present in 69.9% of cases as microbial associations. Therefore, the nasal cavity microflora should

be considered “transient”, which has no etiological significance. Under normal homeostasis, the maxillary sinuses represent a diverse bacterial colonization (several bacteria, both in the form of biofilm and planktonic forms) [8, 10].

Performing any surgical interventions in the oral cavity is accompanied by the risk of contamination of the surgical wound with pathogenic microorganisms, which can be detected even in healthy patients in significant concentrations, and lateral sinus floor augmentation is not an exception. This is a rational basis for prescribing prophylactic antibacterial treatment. In modern clinical practice, the problem of identifying the pathogen of the disease is a component of the permanent process of updating and updating medical and diagnostic protocols and standards for the treatment of infectious and inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region. In this case, various methods of identifying pathogenic microorganisms can be used [11, 12]. When using the cultural identification method in the oral cavity, the pathogen can be identified in 85.50% of patients. In general, associations of microorganisms were determined in 96.00% of cases and monoculture – in 4.00%. At the same time, maximum information can be obtained when using molecular genetic identification methods, especially for anaerobes. In standard cultivation, the families *Streptococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, and *Prevotella spp.* (aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria) are mainly isolated [13, 14].

The resistance of microorganisms to antimicrobial drugs is a special problem in modern medicine; it can be natural or acquired. The first type of resistance is characterized by the absence of target microorganisms for the action of an antimicrobial drug or its unavailability. Acquired resistance occurs as a result of the effect of antimicrobial drugs on microorganisms, especially in low concentrations. In recent decades, special importance has been attached to studying bacterial survival mechanisms. The widespread spread of antibiotic resistance among pathogens of infectious and inflammatory diseases poses a serious threat to the healthcare systems of most countries. Today, it is known that clinical strains of streptococci are the most frequently identified bacteria with resistance to antibiotics, especially penicillins and Clindamycin [15]. Regarding the prophylactic course of antibacterial therapy, the vast majority of clinical recommendations can be found in the use of semi-synthetic protected penicillins (Amoxicillin/Clavulanate), although, given the spread of resistance of oral microbiome participants to beta-lactam antibiotics, the real effectiveness of this group of agents may be quite questionable [16,17]. Recommendations for the initiation of antibiotic therapy before elective surgery, including shortened regimens for

cephalosporins – within 1 day, seem more rational. But choosing the "right" antimicrobial agent for prophylactic therapy is an unresolved question that must be solved in almost every clinical case [18, 19].

The *aim of this study* was to determine the species composition of the participants of the four biotopes of the maxillofacial region (Schneiderian membrane, pharynx, nasal passage, and oral mucosa) of pathogenic and opportunistic microorganisms and their sensitivity to antibiotics in patients during a planned sinus lift.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Biological material (swabs) for bacteriological examination and further identification of microflora was taken from 5 patients during a planned surgical intervention (open sinus lift procedure). The material was taken from the following biotopes: the oral mucosa in the area of the operation before the incisions were made, the surface of the palatine tonsil, the nasal passage on the side of the intervention, and the surface of the internal mucoperiosteum of the maxillary sinus (Schneiderian membrane) after trepanation of the wall of the maxillary sinus and opening of the mucoperiosteum surface. The smears were immediately placed in a sterile gel transport medium (a tube with sterile AMIES gel and an applicator for biological fluids). The material transported to the laboratory was inoculated on the following nutrient media: "Sabouraud Dextrose Agar" (HiMedia Laboratories, India) for the cultivation of microscopic fungi of the genus *Candida*; for hemolytic microflora, in particular bacteria of the genus *Streptococcus* and *Neisseria* – blood agar, *Enterobacteriaceae* – medium "Endo" and "Ploskirev's agar" (HiMedia Laboratories, India), bacteria of the genus *Staphylococcus* were cultivated on "Mannitol Salt Agar" (Biolife, Italy), bacteria of the genus *Enterococcus* - on "Bile esculin agar" (Biolife, Italy). A pure culture of microorganisms was isolated using Gold's sectoral culture method. Identification of microorganisms was carried out according to the morphological, tinctorial, cultural, and biochemical properties of bacteria using "ENTEROtest", "STREPTOtest", "STAPHYLOtest" produced by "Erba Lachema" (Czech Republic). All stages of bacteriological studies, the results of which are presented in this work, were carried out based on the bacteriological laboratory of the Department of Clinical-Laboratory and Morphofunctional Diagnostics of the Dental Faculty of the Uzhhorod National University, Ukraine (head – Dr.Biol.Sc., Prof. M. Kryvtsova). The Bioethics Commission of the Uzhhorod National University approved the protocol of this study. Biological material was collected only with the patients' prior consent.

RESULTS

The studies that were conducted allowed us to reveal an ambiguous picture of the population of different biotopes of the maxillary sinus with bacteria and fungi. Thus, pathogenic microflora was isolated and identified on the oral mucosa in the area of the future surgical wound in 4 out of 5 cases. Among the isolated isolates, representatives of the *Streptococcus* family prevailed (Figure 1). In 2 cases out of 5, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* was isolated in clinically significant concentrations of 10^6 colony-forming units (CFU)/ml. In one case, *Streptococcus pyogenes* was identified in a small amount (10^4 CFU/ml) and *Candida albicans* in a concentration of 2.80×10^1 CFU/ml. Such results are often possible at a dental appointment, since streptococci and yeast-like fungi are the prominent participants in the oral microbiome.

The study of biological material from the nasal passage on the side of the surgical intervention showed a predominance of cases of isolation of bacteria of the *Staphylococci* family (3 cases out of 5, *S. aureus* – 10^3 and 8 CFU/ml, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* – 10^2 CFU/ml) and one case of isolation of streptococci – *Streptococcus viridans*, and only the latter was presented in a clinically significant concentration (10^6). Similar studies conducted with material from the surface of the palatine tonsils showed the presence of both staphylococci and streptococci in the specified biotope. Pathogenic microorganisms were identified in 3 cases out of 5. One case – *S. pyogenes* in a clinically insignificant concentration (1.4×10^3), one – *S. aureus* in the amount of 10^7 CFU/ml. And one case of simultaneous isolation of *S. aureus* in a minimal amount (3 CFU/ml) and *S. pneumoniae* in a clinically significant concentration (10^5 CFU/ml).

The total frequency of isolation of pathogenic microorganisms in such an amount was 40.00%. The most interesting were the results of the bacteriological study of the inner membrane of the maxillary sinus. In this biotope, pathogenic microorganisms were isolated in all cases. Among them, there was one case of simultaneous identification of *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis* in clinically insignificant concentrations (6 and 9 CFU/ml, respectively). All other cases (4 out of 5) were represented by pathogenic microflora in clinically significant concentrations (10^6 CFU/ml) – *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *C. albicans*, and two cases of *S. pneumoniae*.

Subsequently, the sensitivity of the isolated isolates of pathogenic microorganisms to antibiotics was determined using the disk diffusion method. The results showed the presence of antibacterial resistance in isolates in many cases (Table I). All isolated strains were completely resistant to Methicillin. The vast majority of them were resistant to macrolides (Azithromycin and

Clarithromycin). Among cephalosporins, the most resistant bacteria were to Cephalexin, Cefazolin, and Ceftazidime. There was also a significant level of resistance to Amoxicillin/Clavulanate and Carbapenems (Imipenem and Meropenem). Among fluoroquinolones, the most cases of resistance were determined for Moxifloxacin. The most effective among the group of tested antibacterial agents can be considered Ceftriaxone and Cefoperazone/Sulbactam (no resistant isolates were found to these Cephalosporin representatives). A slightly lower level of effectiveness can be predicted when using Cefuroxime, Cefpodoxime, and Cefepime. In the group of fluoroquinolones, Levofloxacin and Gatifloxacin were the most effective. Ciprofloxacin, Ofloxacin, and Norfloxacin showed themselves to be agents with an average level of effectiveness.

Separately, an analysis of antibiotic sensitivity was performed in microorganisms isolated from patients' biotopes in clinically significant concentrations. Such representatives of bacteria were entirely resistant to Cephalexin, Methicillin, and Azithromycin. The isolated microorganisms were mainly resistant to Cefazolin, Amoxicillin/Clavulanate, and Clarithromycin. In half of the cases, bacterial cultures were resistant to carbapenems (Imipenem and Meropenem) (Table II). In ¼ of cases, resistance to Cefuroxime, Ceftazidime, Cefpodoxime, and the vast majority of fluoroquinolones used (Ofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Ciprofloxacin, and Moxifloxacin) was observed. In all cases, the indicated group of microorganisms was moderately sensitive to Cefepime and Levofloxacin. Ceftriaxone and Cefoperazone/Sulbactam were the most effective against such isolates. Cultures were mostly sensitive to Cefuroxime, but the risk of resistance was 25.00%. Gatifloxacin seemed to be quite effective, in which the frequency of cases of sensitivity and moderate sensitivity was distributed equally, without resistance. Such results indicate a tendency to narrow the options for choosing antibacterial agents for a prophylactic course when performing sinus lifting surgery. Fungi found in one clinical case on the mucoperiosteum of the maxillary sinus were sensitive to Fluconazole, Ketoconazole, and Clotrimazole and moderately sensitive to Itraconazole and Nystatin (Table III).

Regarding the sensitivity features of pathogenic microflora that were detected in different biotopes of the maxillofacial area, in this case, all data obtained during the presented study were included in the calculation, including data on the effect of antibacterial agents on microflora detected in clinically insignificant concentrations. The following features of sensitivity to antibacterial agents in microorganisms detected on the oral mucosa were established: complete resistance was observed to first-generation Cephalosporins (Cefazolin and Cephalexin) and

Methicillin and Azithromycin. Half of the identified isolates were resistant to Ceftazidime, Amoxicillin/Clavulanate. One hundred percent sensitivity of the isolated isolates was noted to a number of cephalosporins (Cefuroxime, Ceftriaxone, and Cefoperazone/Sulbactam) and new fluoroquinolones – Gatifloxacin and Moxifloxacin. Moderate sensitivity in the absence of resistance was determined to Cefpodoxime and Cefepime, Ofloxacin, Norfloxacin and Levofloxacin. Normal sensitivity and moderate sensitivity were noted to Ciprofloxacin (Table IV).

Next, antibiotic sensitivity was analyzed in isolates from the surface of the palatine tonsil mucosa. The isolated bacterial cultures were utterly resistant to Cephalexin, Methicillin, and Azithromycin. The vast majority of isolates were resistant to Cefazolin, Ceftazidime, Amoxicillin/Clavulanate, Clarithromycin, Ofloxacin, Norfloxacin, and Ciprofloxacin. In one-third of cases, resistance to carbapenems and Levofloxacin was detected. One hundred percent sensitivity of microflora isolates found on tonsils was observed in Cefuroxime and Ceftriaxone. In two-thirds of cases, sensitivity to Cefoperazone/Sulbactam, Imipenem, Gatifloxacin, and Moxifloxacin was detected. Normal and moderate sensitivity (without resistance) was determined to Cefpodoxime, Cefoperazone/Sulbactam, Gatifloxacin, and Moxifloxacin. Subsequently, in a similar way, antibiotic sensitivity was analyzed in isolates of microorganisms isolated from the nasal passage of patients on the side of sinus lift surgery.

The results showed that microorganisms from the specified biotope were resistant to Cephalexin, Methicillin, Amoxicillin/Clavulanate, and macrolides (Azithromycin and Clarithromycin) in 100.00% of cases. The vast majority of isolates were resistant to Cefazolin, Ceftazidime, and carbapenems (Imipenem and Meropenem). In a third of cases, resistance was observed to all fluoroquinolones, except Levofloxacin (Ofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Ciprofloxacin, Gatifloxacin and Moxifloxacin). One hundred percent sensitivity was observed to individual representatives of the cephalosporin group – to Cefuroxime, Ceftriaxone, and Cefoperazone/Sulbactam. Bacterial cultures were mainly sensitive to Ciprofloxacin and Gatifloxacin, but in a third of cases, resistance to these agents was determined. Only moderate sensitivity was observed to Cefepime. Moderate and marked sensitivity was to Cefpodoxime and Levofloxacin.

The sensitivity of bacterial isolates isolated from patients undergoing sinus lift surgery from the Schneiderian membrane was further analyzed. Such cultures were utterly resistant to Cefazolin, Cephalexin, Methicillin, Meropenem, and Azithromycin. The microorganisms were predominantly

resistant to Amoxicillin/Clavulanate, Imipenem, Clarithromycin, and Ciprofloxacin. In one-third of cases, the microorganisms were resistant to Cefuroxime, Ceftazidime, and Moxifloxacin. The only moderate sensitivity of bacteria was to Cefpodoxime, Cefepime, and half of the fluoroquinolones used (Ofloxacin, Norfloxacin, and Levofloxacin). A moderate sensitivity of cultures was observed to Ceftazidime. Ceftriaxone and Cefoperazone/Sulbactam were found to be the most effective in this biotope. Gatifloxacin can be considered highly effective in the studied biotope, mainly because of its high sensitivity in the absence of resistance.

DISCUSSION

Analysis of the world's professional literature on the study of various biotopes of the maxillary sinus, and Schneiderian membrane when performing planned interventions on the maxillary sinus in particular, shows rather ambiguous and discordant results. Thus, in the work of Carreño Carreño et al. (2018) data are provided that the maxillary sinus was non-sterile in only 18.10% of patients, with bacteria of the *Streptococcus* family prevailing (45.00%), among which *S. viridans* dominated (61.1%). There were also staphylococci (25.00%), among which *S. aureus* prevailed. In addition, *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Klebsiella oxytoca* were isolated, in a third of cases, the culture of microorganisms could not be identified. The isolated microorganisms were resistant to macrolides and had higher sensitivity to penicillins, cephalosporins, and fluoroquinolones. Ampicillin, Amoxicillin/Clavulanate, and Ciprofloxacin were the most effective [20].

Salgado-Peralvo et al. (2022) reported higher efficacy of preoperative antibacterial agents in sinus lift and dental implantation. The positive effect of local administration of Metronidazole solution during surgery was described – sinus irrigation and wetting of osteoplastic material, it was believed that this improves the integration of bone substitute material and promotes the formation of more complete native bone tissue. Penicillins (including Amoxicillin/Clavulanate) are most often chosen; Ciprofloxacin is prescribed in case of allergic reactions to the first group of drugs. Clindamycin and Cefazolin were also recommended [21].

The administration of Azithromycin also helps to reduce the intensity of inflammatory reactions, but this effect can be achieved not only by the antibacterial effect of the drug but also by its side anti-inflammatory effect: Azithromycin in the early stages of the inflammatory process reduces the levels of production of granulocyte colony-stimulating factor, interleukin-6 and interleukin-8, macrophage inflammatory protein 1 and interferon-induced 10 kDa protein.

Azithromycin also reduces the mobilization of granulocyte precursors, as well as the involvement of immune and inflammatory cells during the healing phase. In general, similar effects, similar to immunomodulation, have been recorded in all representatives of the macrolide group, which requires more thorough further study. Therefore, Azithromycin and Clarithromycin are included in the recommended regimens of prophylactic antibacterial therapy when performing dental implantation and sinus lift procedures [22].

The results of Peleg et al. (2019) indicate that in somatically healthy patients when performing sinus lift, the inner membrane is non-sterile (72.00%). Aerobes were identified in 58.00%, anaerobes – 56.00% [23]. In half of the cases, polymicrobial flora was detected. S. On et al. (2019) in a review report the frequency of infectious and inflammatory complications after sinus lifting at 21.00%, mainly of bacterial origin; rare cases were described in terms of the detection of *Aspergillus* fungi and methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* [24].

It is also worth considering the recommendations of one of the founders of the open sinus lift technology: according to the recommendations of Testori (2012), prophylactic antibacterial therapy also included two options – Amoxicillin/Clavulanate (before and after surgery), and for patients with an existing allergy to penicillines – Clarithromycin with Metronidazole. In cases of complications, the first group of patients was recommended Amoxicillin/Clavulanate with Metronidazole, and the second – replacement of antibiotics with Levofloxacin [25].

CONCLUSIONS

A study of the species composition of microorganisms in maxillary sinus and other biotopes of the maxillofacial area in patients who underwent a planned sinus lift operation showed that they differ significantly both in species and in sensitivity to antibacterial agents. In the maxillary sinus, in the absence of clinical signs of inflammation, pathogenic microorganisms were present in clinically significant concentrations – mainly streptococci, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and fungi of the *Candida* genus. Considering the differences in the species composition of different biotopes of the maxillary sinus, as well as the impossibility of complete isolation of the surgical field when performing sinus lifting surgery, there is a high risk of sinus contamination with microflora that persists in the oral cavity and nasal passages during surgery and in the early postoperative period. Therefore, when planning a prophylactic course of antibacterial therapy in the postoperative period, it is advisable to also take into account the sensitivity to antibacterial agents in representatives of all biotopes. Ceftriaxone and Cefoperazone/Sulbactam were the most effective in terms of their

effect on isolates isolated in clinically significant concentrations. The cultures were mainly sensitive to Cefuroxime – $\frac{3}{4}$ of the isolates. Gatifloxacin appeared to be quite effective, with an equal distribution of susceptibility and intermediate susceptibility cases, with no resistance. These results indicate a trend towards a narrowing of the choice of antibacterial agents for prophylactic use during sinus lift surgery. The identified fungi on the mucoperiosteum of the maxillary sinus were sensitive to Fluconazole, Ketoconazole, and Clotrimazole, moderately sensitive to Itraconazole and Nystatin.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: Declared none.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE: The study was approved by Commission of BioEthics of Uzhhorod National University (Decision number: 20.09.2023/01).

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS:

A – Study Design

B – Data Collection

C – Statistical Analysis

D – Data Interpretation

E – Manuscript Preparation

F – Literature Search

I. Mochalov^{A,E,C,D,F}

M. Kryvtsova^{A,B,C,D,E}

S. Tsuperiak^{B,F}

B. Myhajlichenko^{B,E}

N. Guzo^{E,F}

A. Kizim^{E,D,F}

FUNDING: The study was not funded by grants or other financial resources.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

Mochalov I., Kryvtsova M., Tsuperiak et. al. Preprint " THE SPECIES COMPOSITION AND ANTIBIOTIC SENSITIVITY "

REFERENCES

1. Danesh-Sani S.A., Loomer P.M., Wallace S.S.: A comprehensive clinical review of maxillary sinus floor elevation: anatomy, techniques, biomaterials and complications. *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg.*, 2016; 54(7):724-730. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjoms.2016.05.008>
2. Stern A., Green J.: Sinus lift procedures: an overview of current techniques. *Dent Clin North Am.*, 2012; 56(1):219-233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cden.2011.09.003>
3. Al-Dajani M.: Recent Trends in Sinus Lift Surgery and Their Clinical Implications. *Clin Implant Dent Relat Res.*, 2016; 18(1): 204–212. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cid.12275>
4. Shpachynskiy O., Didkovskiy V., Kopchak A.: Radiological changes in maxillary sinus morphology after lateral sinus floor augmentation. *Otolaryngol Pol.*, 2020; 74: 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0014.1679>
5. Tatum H. Jr.: Maxillary and sinus implant reconstructions. *Dent Clin North Am.*, 1986; 30(2):207-229. PMID: 3516738
6. Boyne P.J., James R.A.: Grafting of the maxillary sinus floor with autogenous marrow and bone. *J Oral Surg.*, 1980;38(8):613-616. PMID: 6993637.
7. Fischer J.L., Riley C.A., Kacker A.: Sinonasal Complications Following the Sinus Lift Procedure. *Ochsner J.*, 2023;23(2):147-151. <https://doi.org/10.31486/toj.22.0125>
8. Kim J., Jang H.: A review of complications of maxillary sinus augmentation and available treatment methods. *J Korean Assoc Oral Maxillofac Surg.*, 2019; 45(4):220-224. <https://doi.org/10.5125/jkaoms.2019.45.4.220>
9. Stacchi C., Andolsek F., Berton F. et al.: Intraoperative Complications During Sinus Floor Elevation with Lateral Approach: A Systematic Review. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.*, 2017;32(3):e107-e118. <https://doi.org/10.11607/jomi.4884>
10. Varzhapetian S.D., Gulyuk A.G., Barannik N.G., Strogonova T.V.: Chronic inflammation of the schneiderian membrane of patients with stomatogenous maxillary sinusitis according to the results the data of the lectin histochemistry. *World of Medicine and Biology.*, 2018; 3 (65):17-22. <https://doi.org/10.26724/2079-8334-2018-3-65-17-23>
11. Shuster A., Kleinman S., Reiser V., Ianculovici C., Peleg O., Ben-Ami R.: Short Versus Extended Antibiotic Prophylaxis for Maxillary Sinus Floor Augmentation Via a Lateral Window Approach: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants.*, 2021; 36(5): 992–998. <https://doi.org/10.11607/jomi.8811>

12. Dave M., Barry S., Coulthard P.: An evaluation of sepsis in dentistry. *BrDent J.*, 2021; 230(6): 351–357. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s4141502127246>
13. Böttger S., Zechel Gran S., Schmermund D.: Microbiome of Odontogenic Abscesses. *Microorganisms.*, 2021;9(6): 1307. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9061307>
14. Heim N., Faron A., Wiedemeyer V., Reich R., Martini M.: Microbiology and antibiotic sensitivity of head and neck space infections of odontogenic origin. Differences in inpatient and outpatient management, *J. CranioMaxillofac. Surg.*, 2017; 45: 1731–1735. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcms.2017.07.013>.
15. Heim N., Jürgensen B., Kramer F.J., Wiedemeyer V.: Mapping the microbiological diversity of odontogenic abscess: are we using the right drugs? *Clinical Oral Investig.*, 2021; 25: 187–193. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784020033500>
16. Feres M., Figueiredo L.C., Soares G.M.S., Faver M.: Systemic antibiotics in the treatment of periodontitis. *Periodontology* 2000., 2015; 67(1): 131–186. <https://doi.org/10.1111/prd.12075>
17. Bertossi D., Barone A., Iurlaro A. et al.: Odontogenic Orofacial Infections. *J. Craniofac. Surg.*, 2017; 28: 197–202. <https://doi.org/10.1097/SCS.0000000000003250>
18. Ferenc D., Gverić Grginić A., Prohaska Potočnik C. et al.: Microbial causative agents and their antimicrobial susceptibility patterns in chronic rhinosinusitis – impact on antibiotic prophylaxis and treatment. *Acta Clin Croat.*, 2022; 61(3):511–519. <https://doi.org/10.20471/acc.2022.61.03.17>
19. Rodríguez Sánchez F., Arteagoitia I., Rodríguez Andrés C., Bruers J.: Antibiotic prophylaxis prescribing habits in oral implant surgery in the Netherlands: a cross-sectional survey. *BMC Oral Health.*, 2019; 19(1): 281. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-019-0981-4>
20. Carreño Carreño J., González Jarany M., Gómez Moreno G. et al.: Bacterial influence on consolidation of bone grafts in maxillary sinus elevation. *Clin Oral Implants Res.*, 2016; 27(11): 1431–1438. <https://doi.org/10.1111/clr.12757>
21. Salgado-Peralvo A.O., Garcia-Sanchez A., Kewalramani N. et al.: Consensus Report on Preventive Antibiotic Therapy in Dental Implant Procedures: Summary of Recommendations from the Spanish Society of Implants. *Antibiotics (Basel).*, 2022; 11(5): 655. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11050655>

22. Escalante M.G., Eubank T.D., Leblebicioglu B., Walters J.D.: Comparison of azithromycin and amoxicillin before dental implant placement: An exploratory study of bioavailability and resolution of postoperative inflammation. *J. Periodontol.*, 2015; 86: 1190–1200. <https://doi.org/10.1902/jop.2015.150024>
23. Peleg O., Blinder D., Yudovich K., Yakirevitch A.: Microflora of normal maxillary sinuses: does it justify perioperative antibiotic treatment in sinus augmentation procedures. *Clin Oral Investig.*, 2019; 23(5): 2173–2177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s0078401826620>
24. On S.W., Cho S.W., Yang B.E.: A review of rare complications of maxillary sinus floor augmentation. *J Korean Assoc Oral Maxillofac Surg.*, 2019; 45(6): 351–356. <https://doi.org/10.5125/jkaoms.2019.45.6.351>
25. Testori T., Drago L., Wallace S.S.: Prevention and treatment of postoperative infections after sinus elevation surgery: clinical consensus and recommendations. *Int J Dent.*, 2012; 2012: 365809. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/365809>

Mochalov I., Kryvtsova M., Tsuperiak et. al. Preprint " THE SPECIES COMPOSITION AND ANTIBIOTIC SENSITIVITY ..."